
23. The Maunder Minimum

A PARTICULARLY cold period in Europe, which caused great hardship, was a 70-year interval from around 1645–1715, today known as the ‘Maunder Minimum’. It was so named by US astronomer Jack Eddy (2005).

Eddy drew on the 19th century works of Edward Maunder and Gustav Spörer to link this extended period, some 2°C colder than average, with a seemingly unrelated natural phenomena: during this period of time, sunspots on the face of our Sun all but disappeared.

BEFORE LOOKING at this further (and what it might have to do with Gaia!), let us first look at some links that are known to exist between astronomical phenomena and the Earth’s climate. These are on top of the recent anthropogenic contributions to climate change, which are now uncontested, and other less predictable effects, ranging from El Niño to volcanic eruptions.

The complex orbital motion of the Earth has three dominant components, sometimes referred to as the Milankovitch cycles: the ellipticity of its orbit and the inclination of its spin axis (which give rise to seasonal effects, as well as variations over tens of thousands of years), and the long-term ‘wobble’ of its spin axis (the physical phenomena of precession and nutation).

Together these create short- and long-term variations of the Sun’s radiation reaching the Earth’s surface. And they can explain in large part the episodic nature of the Earth’s glacial and interglacial periods over the last two million years. Shorter-term disturbances of the Earth’s rotation, termed ‘polar motion’, are influenced by less-predictable effects such as ocean currents, wind systems, and even motions in the Earth’s molten core.

ON GEOLOGICAL time-scales, other mechanisms may link our Galactic environment with very long-term climate variability. These include encounters with interstellar clouds (through increasing solar luminosity from accretion, or through shrinking of the Sun’s heliosphere); perturbations of the Oort Cloud due to a passing star, and the injection of comets into the inner solar system; and even ‘ice house’ periods synchronised with spiral arm crossings by our Sun and its solar system.

THE SUN throws in a number of important effects. It spins on its axis once in 27 days, a uniform rotation first detected from the motion of sunspots across its surface. The fluid motions inside the rotating Sun lead, through complex processes still imprecisely understood, to a north–south magnetic field which flips every 11 years, and a related quasi-periodicity in the appearance of cooler surface regions manifesting as sunspots.

Sunspots have been observed and recorded continuously since the early 17th century. We now know that these and other related phenomena (notably, changes in solar radiation and the ejection of solar material, as well as

The Sun's active surface from the SOHO satellite

solar flares and coronal loops) all exhibit a synchronised fluctuation, from active to quiet and back to active again, over this 11-year period.

These various phenomena, known collectively as ‘solar activity’, all arise from the Sun’s rotation, and the continuous regeneration of its magnetic field.

A LINK BETWEEN the variability in solar irradiance and Earth’s climate has been suspected for more than 200 years, since the work of William Herschel.

One of the many questions we can ask is: was the cold period of the 70-year Maunder Minimum linked to the (unexplained) disappearance of sunspots? In other words, does the complex variation of solar activity have a significant effect on Earth’s climate?

In his 1976 study, Eddy gathered data from many sources: historical observations of the Sun going back to the telescope observations of Galileo and others of the 17th and early 18th centuries, historical reports of the aurora borealis observed from Europe and the New World, and sunspots seen with the unaided eye at sunrise and sunset in dynastic records from the Orient.

Varying levels of the carbon isotope ^{14}C are observed in tree rings. Dated through dendrochronology, ^{14}C can actually be used as an indicator of solar activity. Based on its varying levels, Eddy found evidence for other similar periods of a much quieter Sun in the distant past, including an even longer 90-year span, from about 1460 until 1550, which he named the Spörer Minimum.

Both the Maunder and Spörer minima fell during the coldest parts of what climate scientists refer to as the ‘Little Ice Age’, a period extending from the 16th to the 19th centuries. This has suggested a meaningful connection between the longer term behaviour of the Sun and of the Earth’s mean surface temperature.

Contrasting warmer periods have also existed, notably the ‘Medieval Maximum’ around 1000 CE which was accompanied by the migration of the Vikings.

Four hundred years of sunspot observations

THROUGH WHAT mechanism might these relatively small changes in solar activity affect our climate? One idea is that, when the Sun is active, an increased solar wind more effectively reduces the Galactic cosmic ray flux which reaches Earth, producing more ^{14}C . In turn, cosmic rays hitting the atmosphere lead to the ionisation of aerosols in the troposphere, and these could be responsible for the condensation of water droplets and variations in Earth’s cloud cover. These links are hypothesised but unproven, and climatic variations as a result of volcanic activity has also been suggested.

Nevertheless, the known northern hemisphere climatic responses to the Maunder Minimum have been successfully reproduced in global climate model simulations, and these simulations support the idea of solar irradiance variability being capable of altering major modes of dynamical variability in the troposphere.

Meanwhile, recent analysis of cosmogenic radioisotope records from Greenland ice cores, as well as the ^{14}C results from dendrochronology, suggest that the current period of relatively high solar irradiance may perhaps end sometime later this century.

At the same time, and as inferred from the various types of geophysical data, the so-called solar ‘grand minimum’ events (periods over which several solar cycles exhibit lower than average activity for decades or centuries) appear to be more randomised than periodic.

IN THE USUAL SPIRIT of scientific endeavour, we would like to be able to test the hypothesis that these solar ‘grand minima’ affect Earth’s climate. And we would like to understand how often they occur for our Sun. Is the present cycle of solar activity unusual or transitory, and are Maunder-type minima common phenomena in other stars like the Sun?

Going further back in time to search for these dependencies has reached the limits of what appears possible on Earth. But an ingenious approach has tackled the problem using the data from Gaia’s forerunner Hipparcos: instead of trying to estimate the prevalence of our Sun’s grand minima over, say, 100–1000 years, we can instead make a survey of the magnetic activity of Sun-like stars in our solar neighbourhood.

If we can choose stars whose properties are very close to those of the Sun, we can then try to argue that the fraction of solar-type stars showing evidence of very low activity corresponds to an estimate of the fraction of the Sun’s own lifetime spent in a grand minimum state.

WHAT CONSTITUTES a Sun-like star? Ideally, we would like to seek out non-binary stars which are essentially identical to the Sun in all its astrophysical properties: mass, age, luminosity, chemistry, temperature, surface gravity, magnetic field, rotation velocity, microturbulence, and chromospheric activity.

Some early surveys of Sun-like stars with low activity, using chromospheric emission in the lines of Ca H and K, suggested that perhaps 30% of Sun-like stars appeared to be in these low-activity states (Baliunas & Jastrow, 1990). Henry et al. (1996) observed more than 800 stars within 50 pc, and concluded that only some 10% were inactive. If the observations are considered to be a sequence of snapshots of the Sun during its life, then the Sun will spend about 10% of the remainder of its main-sequence life in Maunder minimum-type phases.

Wright (2004) used accurate Hipparcos parallaxes for stars within 60 pc to figure out their location with respect to the main sequence which, from stellar evolutionary models, yields their age. He showed that nearly all stars previously classified as Maunder-minimum candidates were actually evolved stars, and that it was not obvious how to identify such a state from a single observation. However, long-term monitoring programmes suggest that Sun-like stars exhibit a variety of activity behaviour, including solar-like cycles and flat-activity states. If the Sun’s Maunder Minimum was a transition between the two, then continued monitoring should detect some stars switching between them.

Lubin et al. (2012) identified 15 very inactive stars, ranked in priority order as Maunder Minimum candidates. Their high-accuracy Gaia data are ready to serve as proxies for probing the climatic variations on Earth.